

A Note on Path Signed Digraphs

P. Siva Kota Reddy[†] S. Vijay[‡] and H. C. Savithri*

[†]Department of Mathematics, Rajeev Institute of Technology, Industrial Area,
B-M Bypass Road, Hassan 573 201, India

[‡]Department of Mathematics, Govt. First Grade College, Kadur, Chikkamangalore 577 548, India

*Department of Computer Science & Engineering, Rajeev Institute of Technology,
Industrial Area, B-M Bypass Road, Hassan 573 201, India

E-mail: reddy_math@yahoo.com

Abstract: A *Smarandachely k -signed digraph* (*Smarandachely k -marked digraph*) is an ordered pair $S = (D, \sigma)$ ($S = (D, \mu)$) where $D = (V, \mathcal{A})$ is a digraph called *underlying digraph of S* and $\sigma : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow (\bar{e}_1, \bar{e}_2, \dots, \bar{e}_k)$ ($\mu : V \rightarrow (\bar{e}_1, \bar{e}_2, \dots, \bar{e}_k)$) is a function, where each $\bar{e}_i \in \{+, -\}$. Particularly, a Smarandachely 2-signed digraph or Smarandachely 2-marked digraph is called abbreviated a *signed digraph* or a *marked digraph*. In this paper, we define the path signed digraph $\vec{P}_k(S) = (\vec{P}_k(D), \sigma')$ of a given signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$ and offer a structural characterization of signed digraphs that are switching equivalent to their 3-path signed digraphs $\vec{P}_3(S)$. The concept of a line signed digraph is generalized to that of a path signed digraphs. Further, in this paper we discuss the structural characterization of path signed digraphs $\vec{P}_k(S)$.

Key Words: Smarandachely k -Signed digraphs, Smarandachely k -marked digraphs, signed digraphs, marked digraphs, balance, switching, path signed digraphs, line signed digraphs, negation.

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§1. Introduction

For standard terminology and notion in digraph theory, we refer the reader to the classic textbooks of Bondy and Murty [2] and Harary et al. [4]; the non-standard will be given in this paper as and when required.

A *Smarandachely k -signed digraph* (*Smarandachely k -marked digraph*) is an ordered pair $S = (D, \sigma)$ ($S = (D, \mu)$) where $D = (V, \mathcal{A})$ is a digraph called *underlying digraph of S* and $\sigma : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow (\bar{e}_1, \bar{e}_2, \dots, \bar{e}_k)$ ($\mu : V \rightarrow (\bar{e}_1, \bar{e}_2, \dots, \bar{e}_k)$) is a function, where each $\bar{e}_i \in \{+, -\}$. Particularly, a Smarandachely 2-signed digraph or Smarandachely 2-marked digraph is called abbreviated a *signed digraph* or a *marked digraph*. A *signed digraph* is an ordered pair $S = (D, \sigma)$, where

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²The third author is B.E student at Department of Computer Science & Engineering, Rajeev Institute of Technology, Hassan. This is her first research contribution.

$D = (V, \mathcal{A})$ is a digraph called *underlying digraph of S* and $\sigma : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \{+, -\}$ is a function. A *marking of S* is a function $\mu : V(D) \rightarrow \{+, -\}$. A signed digraph S together with a marking μ is denoted by S_μ . A signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$ is *balanced* if every semicycle of S is positive (See [4]). Equivalently, a signed digraph is balanced if every semicycle has an even number of negative arcs. The following characterization of balanced signed digraphs is obtained in [9].

Proposition 1.1(E. Sampathkumar et al. [9]) *A signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$ is balanced if, and only if, there exist a marking μ of its vertices such that each arc \vec{uv} in S satisfies $\sigma(\vec{uv}) = \mu(u)\mu(v)$.*

In [9], the authors define switching and cycle isomorphism of a signed digraph as follows:

Let $S = (D, \sigma)$ and $S' = (D', \sigma')$, be two signed digraphs. Then S and S' are said to be isomorphic, if there exists an isomorphism $\phi : D \rightarrow D'$ (that is a bijection $\phi : V(D) \rightarrow V(D')$ such that if \vec{uv} is an arc in D then $\phi(u)\phi(v)$ is an arc in D') such that for any arc $\vec{e} \in D$, $\sigma(\vec{e}) = \sigma'(\phi(\vec{e}))$.

Given a marking μ of a signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$, *switching S* with respect to μ is the operation changing the sign of every arc \vec{uv} of S by $\mu(u)\sigma(\vec{uv})\mu(v)$. The signed digraph obtained in this way is denoted by $S_\mu(S)$ and is called *μ switched signed digraph* or just *switched signed digraph*.

Further, a signed digraph S switches to signed digraph S' (or that they are switching equivalent to each other), written as $S \sim S'$, whenever there exists a marking of S such that $S_\mu(S) \cong S'$.

Two signed digraphs $S = (D, \sigma)$ and $S' = (D', \sigma')$ are said to be *cycle isomorphic*, if there exists an isomorphism $\phi : D \rightarrow D'$ such that the sign $\sigma(Z)$ of every semicycle Z in S equals to the sign $\sigma(\phi(Z))$ in S' .

Proposition 1.2(E. Sampathkumar et al. [9]) *Two signed digraphs S_1 and S_2 with the same underlying graph are switching equivalent if, and only if, they are cycle isomorphic.*

§2. Path Signed Digraphs

In [3], Harary and Norman introduced the notion of line digraphs for digraphs. The *line digraph $L(D)$* of a given digraph $D = (V, \mathcal{A})$ has the arc set $\mathcal{A} := \mathcal{A}(D)$ of D for its vertex set and (e, f) is an arc in $L(D)$ whenever the arcs e and f in D have a vertex in common in such a way that it is the head of e and the tail of f ; hence, a given digraph H is called a *line digraph* if there exists a digraph D such that $L(D) \cong H$. By a natural way, Broersma and Li [1] generalized the concept of line digraphs to that of directed path graphs.

Let k be a positive integer, and denote \vec{P}_k or \vec{C}_k a directed path or a directed cycle on k vertices, respectively. Let D be a digraph containing at least one directed path \vec{P}_k . Denote $\Pi_k(D)$, the set of all \vec{P}_k 's of D . Then the *directed \vec{P}_k -graph* of D , denoted by $\vec{P}_k(D)$, is the digraph with vertex set $\Pi_k(D)$; pq is an arc of $\vec{P}_k(D)$ if, and only if, there is a \vec{P}_{k+1} or $\vec{C}_k = (v_1v_2\dots v_{k+1})$ in D (with $v_1 = v_{k+1}$ in the case of a \vec{C}_k) such that $p = v_1v_2\dots v_k$ and

$q = v_2 \dots v_k v_{k+1}$. Note that $\vec{P}_1(D) = D$ and $\vec{L}(D)$. In [7], the authors proposed an open problem for further study, i.e., how to give a characterization for directed \vec{P}_3 -graphs.

We extend the notion of $\vec{P}_k(D)$ to the realm of signed digraphs. In a signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$, where $D = (V, \mathcal{A})$ is a digraph called *underlying digraph of S* and $\sigma : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \{+, -\}$ is a function. The *path signed digraph* $\vec{P}_k(S) = (\vec{P}_k(D), \sigma')$ of a signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$ is a signed digraph whose underlying digraph is $\vec{P}_k(D)$ called *path digraph* and sign of any arc $e = \vec{P}_k \vec{P}'_k$ in $\vec{P}_k(S)$ is $\sigma'(\vec{P}_k \vec{P}'_k) = \sigma(\vec{P}_k) \sigma(\vec{P}'_k)$. Further, a signed digraph $S = (G, \sigma)$ is called *path signed digraph*, if $S \cong \vec{P}_k(S')$, for some signed digraph S' . At the end of this section, we discuss the structural characterization of path signed digraphs $\vec{P}_k(S)$. We now give a straightforward, yet interesting, property of path signed digraphs.

Proposition 2.1 *For any signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$, its path signed digraph $\vec{P}_k(S)$ is balanced.*

Proof Since sign of any arc $\sigma'(e = \vec{P}_k \vec{P}'_k)$ in $\vec{P}_k(S)$ is $\sigma(\vec{P}_k) \sigma(\vec{P}'_k)$, where σ is the marking of $\vec{P}_k(S)$, by Proposition 1.1, $\vec{P}_k(S)$ is balanced. \square

Remark: For any two signed digraphs S and S' with same underlying digraph, their path signed digraphs are switching equivalent.

In [9], the authors defined line signed digraph of a signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$ as follows:

A *line signed digraph* $L(S)$ of a signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$ is a signed digraph $L(S) = (L(D), \sigma')$ where for any arc ee' in $L(D)$, $\sigma'(ee') = \sigma(\vec{e}) \sigma(\vec{e}')$ (see also, E. Sampathkumar et al. [8]).

Hence, we shall call a given signed digraph S a *line signed digraph* if it is isomorphic to the line signed digraph $L(S')$ of some signed digraph S' . By the definition of path signed digraphs, we observe that $\vec{P}_2(S) = L(S)$.

Corollary 2.2 *For any signed digraph $S = (G, \sigma)$, its $\vec{P}_2(S)$ ($=L(S)$) is balanced.*

In [9], the authors obtain structural characterization of line signed digraphs as follows:

Proposition 2.3(E. Sampathkumar et al. [9]) *A signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$ is a line signed digraph (or \vec{P}_2 -signed digraph) if, and only if, S is balanced signed digraph and its underlying digraph D is a line digraph (or \vec{P}_2 -digraph).*

Proof Suppose that S is balanced and D is a line digraph. Then there exists a digraph D' such that $L(D') \cong D$. Since S is balanced, by Proposition 1.1, there exists a marking μ of D such that each arc \vec{uv} in S satisfies $\sigma(\vec{uv}) = \mu(u) \mu(v)$. Now consider the signed digraph $S' = (D', \sigma')$, where for any arc \vec{e} in D' , $\sigma'(\vec{e})$ is the marking of the corresponding vertex in D . Then clearly, $L(S') \cong S$. Hence S is a line signed digraph.

Conversely, suppose that $S = (D, \sigma)$ is a line signed digraph. Then there exists a signed digraph $S' = (D', \sigma')$ such that $L(S') \cong S$. Hence D is the line digraph of D' and by Corollary 2.2, S is balanced. \square

We strongly believe that the above Proposition can be generalized to path signed digraphs

$\vec{P}_k(S)$ for $k \geq 3$. Hence, we pose it as a problem:

Problem 2.4 *If $S = (D, \sigma)$ is a balanced signed digraph and its underlying digraph D is a path digraph, then S is a path signed digraph.*

§3. Switching Equivalence of Signed Digraphs and Path Signed Digraphs

Broersma and Li [1] concluded that the only connected digraphs D with $\vec{P}_3(D) \cong D$ consists of a directed cycle with in-trees or out-trees attached to its vertices, with at most non-trivial trees, where a directed tree T of D is an *out-tree* of D if $V(T) = V(D)$ and precisely one vertex of T has in-degree zero (the root of T), while all other vertices of T have in-degree one, and an *in-tree* of D is defined analogously with respect to out-degrees.

Proposition 3.1 (Broersma and Hoede [1]) *Let D be connected digraph without sources or sinks. If D has an in-tree or out-tree, then $\vec{P}_3(D) \cong D$ if, and only if, $D \cong \vec{C}_n$ for some $n \geq 3$. Hence, if D is strongly connected, then $\vec{P}_3(D) \cong D$ if, and only if, $D \cong \vec{C}_n$ for some $n \geq 3$.*

In the view of the above result, we now characterize signed digraphs that are switching equivalent to their \vec{P}_3 -signed digraphs.

Proposition 3.2 *For any strongly connected signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$, $S \sim \vec{P}_3(S)$ if, and only if, S is balanced and $D \cong \vec{C}_n$ for some $n \geq 3$.*

Proof Suppose $S \sim L(S)$. This implies, $D \cong L(D)$ and hence by Proposition 3.1, $D \cong \vec{C}_n$. Now, if S is signed digraph, then by Corollary 2.2, implies that $L(S)$ is balanced and hence if S is unbalanced its line signed digraph $L(S)$ being balanced cannot be switching equivalent to S in accordance with Proposition 1.2. Therefore, S must be balanced.

Suppose that S is balanced and $D \cong \vec{C}_n$ for some $n \geq 3$. Then, by Proposition 2.1, $\vec{P}_3(S)$ is balanced, the result follows from Proposition 1.2. \square

In [9], the authors defined a signed digraph S is *periodic*, if $L^{n+k}(S) \sim L^n(S)$ for some positive integers n and k .

Analogous to the line signed digraphs, we defined periodic for $\vec{P}_3(S)$ as follows:

For some positive integers n and k , define that a path signed digraph $\vec{P}_3(S)$ is periodic, if $\vec{P}_3^{n+k}(S) \sim \vec{P}_3^n(S)$.

Proposition 3.3 (Broersma and Hoede [1]) *If D is strongly connected digraph and $\vec{P}_3^n(D) \cong D$ for some $n \geq 1$, then $\vec{P}_3(D) \cong D$ and D is a directed cycle.*

The following result is follows from Propositions 2.1, 3.2 and 3.3.

Proposition 3.4 *If S is strongly connected signed digraph, and $\vec{P}_3^n(S) \sim S$ for some $n \geq 1$, then $\vec{P}_3(S) \sim S$ and D is a directed cycle.*

The *negation* $\eta(S)$ of a given signed digraph S defined as follows: $\eta(S)$ has the same underlying digraph as that of S with the sign of each arc opposite to that given to it in S .

However, this definition does not say anything about what to do with nonadjacent pairs of vertices in S while applying the unary operator $\eta(\cdot)$ of taking the negation of S .

For a signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$, the $\vec{P}_k(S)$ is balanced (Proposition 2.1). We now examine, the condition under which negation of $\vec{P}_k(S)$ (i.e., $\eta(\vec{P}_k(S))$) is balanced.

Proposition 3.5 *Let $S = (D, \sigma)$ be a signed digraph. If $\vec{P}_k(D)$ is bipartite then $\eta(\vec{P}_k(S))$ is balanced.*

proof Since, by Proposition 2.1, $\vec{P}_k(S)$ is balanced, then every semicycle in $\vec{P}_k(S)$ contains even number of negative arcs. Also, since $\vec{P}_k(G)$ is bipartite, all semicycles have even length; thus, the number of positive arcs on any semicycle C in $\vec{P}_k(S)$ are also even. This implies that the same thing is true in negation of $\vec{P}_k(S)$. Hence $\eta(\vec{P}_k(S))$ is balanced. \square

Proposition 3.2 provides easy solutions to three other signed digraph switching equivalence relations, which are given in the following results.

Corollary 3.6 *For any signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$, $\eta(S) \sim \vec{P}_3(S)$ if, and only if, S is an unbalanced signed digraph on any odd semicycle.*

Corollary 3.7 *For any signed digraph $S = (D, \sigma)$ and for any integer $k \geq 1$, $\vec{P}_k(\eta(S)) \sim \vec{P}_k(S)$.*

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